

IX-XI CENTURIES DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL THOUGHTS AND EDUCATIONAL-ETHICAL THOUGHTS DURING THE EASTERN RENAISSANCE.

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Abstract: In this article, the views of great thinkers and their works on the development of pedagogical ideas and educational-ethical ideas during the Eastern Renaissance of the 9th-11th centuries are presented. now in the sense of the Academy) information is also given.

Key words: House of Wisdom, Academy, Renaissance period of culture, thinkers.

During the reign of Caliph Harun al-Rashid (786-833 AD) and his son al-Ma'mun, the "Bayt-ul-Hikma" ("House of Wisdom") (now the Academy) was established in Baghdad. . This Academy will become a scientific center for all scientists. A world library was established under him. The Academy further developed in 813-833. There was also an observatory at the Academy, and later a new library was built. This science center in Baghdad, in turn, influenced the development of science and spiritual life in the East and West. In this place, it is worth noting the patronage of Caliph al-Ma'mun in the development of science. After all, Caliph al-Ma'mun valued science very much.

Even when he was the deputy of the caliphate in Khurasan from the beginning of the 9th century, he gathered scientists from Movarounnahr and Khurasan and created conditions for their scientific creativity. Among them were our compatriot scholars such as al-Khorazmi, al-Khuttali, al-Javahari, al-Farghani, al-Marazvi. When Al-Ma'mun sat on the throne of the caliphate, he called all the scientists to Baghdad, and in "Bayt-ul-Hikma" - the house of wisdom ("Ma'mun Academy"), science flourished in cooperation with Arab scientists. as well as ancient cultural monuments, whether they are Greek, Arab, Movarounnahr and Khurasan peoples of the most ancient times, served as the basis for the creation and development of the culture of the Renaissance. If the Arabs conquered Central Asia and lost the foci of science and culture that existed here before, then the ancient scientific tradition was gradually restored, and as a result mature figures of science grew up. starts to come out. As a result of the combination of all these, a whole culture is formed and begins to develop in the East.

In fact, during this period, the economy developed, agriculture, handicrafts developed. During this period, the land used for agriculture expanded, many

irrigated lands were opened, irrigation facilities were restored, new ones were built, cotton, flax, hemp were planted, and cloth was woven from their fibers.

Textile products of Khorezm, Urganch, Ferghana, Samarkand and Bukhara, especially silk of Samarkand and Bukhara, became famous in Movarounnahr. The development of agriculture, crafts, and industrial products paved the way for the development of trade. As a result, the volume of trade between the countries of the Near and Middle East with foreign countries: Spain, India, China, and Byzantium increased. The conquest of the Iberian Peninsula by the Arabs opened new pages of human history. The importance of this process, especially for Europe, was incomparable. The East not only influenced the development of European culture, but also fundamentally changed the historical process of the psychology, thinking, character, and way of life of European people. This, in turn, affected mathematics, philosophy, astronomy, natural sciences, medicine, manners, lifestyle, and socio-economic life.

From the 10th century, the collapse of the caliphate in the emergence of independent feudal states in Movarunnahr and Khorasan - Tahirids, Somanids, Karakhanids, Ghaznavids, Seljuks, Khorezmshahs - also led to the development of cultural life. During this period, money circulation developed. Changes in the political, socio-economic life of the society will definitely have an impact on the cultural life.

Mary, Bukhara, Samarkand and Urganch were the cultural centers of that time in the Somani state. During this period, Arabic was the language of science and communication. Classes in schools were conducted in Arabic. Official documents and Sharia rules were written in Arabic. Scientific works were also written in Arabic. By the middle of the 10th century, Persian-Tajik language was also used. However, documents and works were written in Persian-Tajik language, but they were written in Arabic spelling. It is mentioned in the sources that even ordinary children from the surrounding villages came to study in the schools in these cities. At that time, there was a big book market in Bukhara. Scholars and virtuous people met in bookstores and held scientific dialogues and discussions.

Abu Ali ibn Sina tells in his biography that he bought Farabi's commentaries on Aristotle's "Metaphysics" in one of the bookstores. There was a large library in the palace of the emir of Bukhara. They recognized Amir's library as the only library that could compete with the Shiraz library of that time.

Thinkers such as Rudaki, Firdawsi, al-Khorazmi, al-Farghani, Abu Rayhan Beruni and Abu Ali ibn Sina created during the Samanid period. In the state of the

Karakhanids, which was formed in the second half of the 10th century, some khans established libraries in their palaces. These libraries contained the works of Arab and even Western European scholars. During this period, the Turkish language was formed. Scientists such as Yusuf Khos Hajib and Mahmud Kashgari created works of world importance. At the beginning of the 11th century, the state of the Ghaznavids, later the state of the Seljuks and Khorezmshahs was established. During the Ghaznavid period, scientific, socio-philosophical ideas developed. Mahmoud Ghaznavi collected a lot of cultural wealth in his palace, invited scientists to scientific work. For example, Abu Rayhan created Beruni's famous work "India" here.

During the Seljuk era, when Alp-Arslan Muhammad was in power, his minister Nizam ul-Mulk was a famous political figure and one of the most enlightened people of his time. The Seljuk power was militarized, and the internal and external policy of this power was managed by Nizam ul-Mulk. He made some changes to the working method of the Ghaznavids, developed a method of managing the power and created his "policy book" (1091-1092). This work describes the principles of state management. Nizam ul-Mulk does a great service in the development of education.

In 1067, he built the most famous educational institution of that time - "Nizomiya" madrasa in Baghdad with his personal funds. He pays great attention to scientists, religious leaders, and Sufis. Another of his great merits is that he reformed the calendar. In 1074, he created a calendar-calendar for the countries of the Middle East, which is considered one of the most improved calendars so far.

Science develops in Khorezm in the 11th century. King Ma'mun II of Khorezm invited outstanding scientists to his court. "Bayt-ul-Hikma" - the House of Wise Men, which he founded, left its name in history as "Ma'mun Academy". Scholars such as Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, historian Miskawayh, mathematician Abu Nasr ibn Iraq, philosopher Abu Sahl al-Masikhi, physician Abul Khair Hammar were involved in the development of this academy. In Movarounnahr and Khorasan by the 9th century, the spiritual uplift led to the beginning of the Eastern Renaissance. Muhammad Musa al-Khorazmi, Abu Nasr, a philosopher and astrologer who is world-famous for his services in the field of science and enlightenment, who left a name for his scientific legacy in the fields of mathematics, physics, medicine, history, language and literature, and pedagogy in Movarounnahr. Encyclopedic scholars such as Farabi, Ahmad al-Farghani, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina were active. In their scientific

heritage, encyclopedists paid great attention to the creation of educational and moral works, and the ideas presented in these works are of great importance in the development of a person's mental, moral, aesthetic and physical development, and in the development of pedagogical thought. They also created pure pedagogical works during the period of the Eastern Renaissance, and produced educationalists who left a name for themselves with their immortal teachings about the special and general methods of human development in education.

References:

- 1 Юнусалиева, Наргизахон. "Изучение зарубежного опыта для оценки профессиональной компетентности сотрудника." *Scientific progress* 2.2 (2021): 354-358.
- 2 Nargiza, Yunusalieva. "Social and moral education of students and development of values." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 10.1 (2022): 300-305.
- 3 Najmiddinovna, Rahimova Feruza, and Muxammadiev Baxromjon Baxtiyorjon o'g'li. "Factors affecting the social pedagogical activity of multimedia." *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429 11.05 (2022): 114-118.
- 4 Najmiddinovna, Rahimova Feruza. "THE DESCRIPTION OF MULTIMEDIA VOCITAS AS AN INTEGRATIVE UNIT FOR IMPROVING THE SOCIAL PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS." *American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development* 15 (2023): 265-267.
- 5 Рахимова, Феруза. "Multimedia vositalarining ijtimoiy pedagogik faoliyatga ta'sir etuvchi omillari." *Современные тенденции инновационного развития науки и образования в глобальном мире* 1.4 (2022): 20-26.
- 6 Najmiddinovna, Rahimova Feruza. "The Unique Power Of Improving The Social Pedagogical Activity Of Students In Multimedia Vocitas." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 11.6 (2023): 604-606.
- 7 Najmiddinovna, Rahimova Feruza. "Factors Affecting The Socio-Pedagogical Activity Of Students In Multimedia Lectures." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 11.6 (2023): 601-603.

